

Core-Shell Nanotubes from Tungsten/Molybdenum Ditelluride-Tungsten Disulfide via Van der Waals Epitaxy

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TOC

Abstract

Tungsten ditelluride and molybdenum ditelluride in the form of nanotubes were materialized as core-shell structures with tungsten disulfide layers. The variability of the described protocols allows the formation of WS₂@WTe₂, reversed WTe₂@WS₂, and, by combining both approaches, multilayer WTe₂@WS₂@WTe₂. Alternatively, WS₂@MoTe₂ or even WTe₂@WS₂@MoTe₂ nanotubes were synthesized. Deposition of the telluride layers was achieved via Van der Waals epitaxial growth. The synthesized nanostructures were characterized by advanced imaging techniques revealing hexagonal 2H and orthorhombic 1T' polymorph motifs for WS₂ and WTe₂ layers, respectively. In the case of MoTe₂ nanotubes, the structural cascade of 2H-WS₂@2H-MoTe₂@1T'-MoTe₂ was elucidated. Complex heterostructures were inspected by 4D scanning transmission electron microscopy position resolved diffraction, revealing their chiral nature. Mechanistic aspects of the synthesis were briefly studied. Moreover, tellurium-substituted WS₂ nanotubes were synthesized and characterized. Tungsten ditelluride-disulfide nanotubes complete the family of tungsten dichalcogenide nanotubular structures.

Introduction

Tungsten^[1-7] and molybdenum^[8-12] ditellurides are attracting widespread interest in the solid-state physics community these days. Mainly, WTe₂ is a topological insulator and superconductor at low temperatures.^[1] It is a Type II Weyl semimetal in which the quantum spin Hall effect was detected and potentially the matrix for inducing Majorana states (quasiparticles, which are their own antiparticles relevant to quantum computers).^[13-15] Moreover, non-saturated, extremely large magnetoresistance was found in WTe₂ at low temperatures (0.5 K).^[16] Thus, when a large magnetic field (60 T) is applied along the *c*-axis, the electrical resistance increases by seven orders of magnitude. Tungsten ditelluride adopts a distorted 1T lattice structure (1T') formed by six tellurium atoms octahedrally coordinated to the tungsten atoms. While the 1T' structure of WTe₂ is semimetallic, the compound arranged into the 2H polytype is semiconducting.^[1,17-19] Many interesting properties emerged from this unique structure, some of which were predicted and others already measured.

One of the most important features of 2D layered materials and their electronic and optical properties is their effective tunability, which is accomplished by applying a uniaxial and biaxial strain to their structure.^[20-22] That could be achieved by the deposition of the studied material on a polymeric film and the application of the force by pulling or bending. However, this method could suffer from major drawbacks related to the fabricated device's adhesion, stability, and overall performance. Another and much more elegant method to apply uniaxial strain is the preparation of nanotubes from the relevant 2D material. Nanotubes are a 1D nanoscopic stable structure with inner strain, which benefits from high stability and crystallinity.^[23-26] The combination of quasi-1D structure and chirality of the nanotubes results in the loss of inversion and time-reversal symmetries, lending itself to low-temperature superconductivity and Little-Park oscillations.^[27] Furthermore, it leads to the emergence of the bulk photovoltaic effect and other interesting optoelectronic phenomena.^[28,29] Accessible manipulation of such nanotubes was essential for their electronic exploitation and device fabrication.

Tungsten ditelluride in the form of nanotubes has been studied *in silico*.^[30] WTe₂ nanotubes have not been synthesized so far due to various factors, mainly the collapse of the structures into the nanowires and plate formation. A possible reason for WTe₂ wire formation instead of the nanotubes was proposed as volume differences between precursor WO_{3-x} nanowhisker (as unit cell volume per the number of W atoms, $49.0 \times 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and the resulting material ($75.8 \times 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^{-3}$).^[31]

Such issues are overcome in the present study, where WTe₂ is deposited onto van der Waals structural scaffold^[32] of a WS₂ nanotube. The to-be-described synthetic protocol allows great variability of layer-by-layer assembly. Scheme 1 foreshadows the synthesized materials in a graphical scheme. The very starting material is a W₁₈O₄₉ nanowhisker, which serves as a sacrificial templating precursor. Well-known reductive sulfidation of this material at elevated temperatures yields multilayer WS₂ nanotubes (Scheme 1a).^[33,34] The prematurely interrupted sulfidation reaction produces tungsten suboxide nanowhisker wrapped by several WS₂ layers (Scheme 1b). Tungsten disulfide nanotubes with partially substituted sulfur atoms by tellurium could be synthesized by mixed sulfidation-telluridation reaction (Scheme 1c). Utilizing tungsten disulfide nanotubes blended with tungsten trioxide particles as precursor forms core-shell WS₂@WTe₂ inorganic multilayer nanotubes (Scheme 1d). Careful telluridation of tungsten suboxide nanowhisker with several enveloping layers of WS₂ forms reverse WTe₂@WS₂ nanotubular material (Scheme 1e). Combining the stated reactions, a heterogenous core-shell-shell WTe₂@WS₂@WTe₂ nanotube is reached (Scheme 1f). For WS₂@MoTe₂, a similar chart could be constructed where the used precursor is MoO₃ and tellurium vapor. This additional variability allows the deposition of both tungsten and molybdenum ditelluride layers within and outside the WS₂ nanotube, respectively (modified Scheme 1f). Such nanomaterial is characterized as an exotic core-shell-shell WTe₂@WS₂@MoTe₂ nanotube. The synthesized nanotubes were characterized mainly by

high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM), high-resolution scanning transmission electron microscopy (HRSTEM) coupled with high-angle annular dark-field imaging (HAADF), and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). The electronic structure of was probed by low loss electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS). Special emphasis was targeted on structural arrangement through classical side projection and cross-sectional views.

Scheme 1. Graphical scheme of the synthesis of core-shell and mixed tungsten disulfide-ditelluride nanotubes.

Results and Discussion

Initially, the reactivity of $W_{18}O_{49}$ nanowhiskers in sulfidation and telluridation processes was briefly studied to enlighten the reason behind their divergent pathways (Figure 1S). Comparison of the telluridation (Figure 1Sa) and sulfidation (Figure 1Sb) of $W_{18}O_{49}$ nanowhiskers interrupted after 10 minutes showed different outcomes. In the case of WS_2 growth, the tungsten oxide surface was enveloped by several layers of WS_2 , creating a passivation layer. This cylindrical nanostructure was accomplished through the sacrificial conversion of the outer $W_{18}O_{49}$ surface into a few closed layers of WS_2 .^[33] On the contrary, telluridation did not produce a core-shell $W_{18}O_{49}@WTe_2$ structure but reacted from the whisker's tip, readily forming a WTe_2 plate or wire (Figure 1Sa). The formation of the WS_2 shell, as described in the mechanistic study of WS_2 nanotube growth,^[34] is essential for nanowhisker-to-nanotube conversion. Therefore, missing this initial step prevents direct conversion of the $W_{18}O_{49}$ nanowhisker into WTe_2 nanotube.

To reach WTe_2 in the nanotubular structure, van der Waals epitaxy was utilized to deposit WTe_2 layers onto the preexisting WS_2 nanotubes. Pristine WS_2 nanotubes were mixed with fine WO_3 powder and tellurized at elevated temperatures in the forming gas atmosphere. Figure 1 shows a microscopical analysis of the core-shell-shell $WTe_2@WS_2@WTe_2$ nanotube obtained according to the reaction schematically described in Scheme 1f. Figure 1a displays a combination of STEM-HAADF imaging and STEM-EDS elemental mapping of S, Te, and W. The tellurium signal (green) shows the possible scroll character of the outer WTe_2 layers deposited onto the WS_2 nanotube (blue and red). Surprisingly, the nanotube lumen also contains tellurium, showing internal deposition of WTe_2 layers, a phenomenon further studied and described in the upcoming text. The outer layers were studied in detail (Figure 1b) by HRSTEM-HAADF and elemental mapping. The multilayered structure consists of the inner 2H- WS_2 phase and four outer tubular walls of WTe_2 in 1T' arrangement. Interestingly, the outer WTe_2 layers are

deposited in pairs, which are distinguishable by the folding angle. The very outer two layers showed a clear lattice arrangement of WTe_2 coincident with the $\langle 100 \rangle$ view. The two layers beneath (closer to the nanotube center) hold an approximate $50\text{-}60^\circ$ angle, showing the WTe_2 lattice along the $\langle 110 \rangle$ or $\langle 320 \rangle$ axes. Further, the lattice model of the respective $1T'$ - WTe_2 layers is overlaid on the HRTEM image, capturing the complex nanotubular structure. The chemical difference between the WS_2 and WTe_2 layers was also determined by elemental mapping, as shown in the right part of Figure 1b. Another $WS_2@WTe_2$ nanotube and a cross-section of the nanotube, together with fullerene-like nanoparticles of the same composition, are displayed in Figure 2S. The Raman spectrum of such nanotube is shown in Figure 3Sa with signals corresponding to both WS_2 and WTe_2 .^[35,36]

Figure 1. Imaging of $WTe_2@WS_2@WTe_2$ nanotube. a) STEM-HAADF and EDS elemental mapping displays the distribution of Te (green), S (red), and W (blue) in the multiplayer nanotube. b) detailed HRSTEM-HAADF imaging of the outer nanotube layers and the WS_2/WTe_2 interface. The lattices of WS_2 and WTe_2 are marked by models. The right parts show the elemental mapping.

The nanotube in Figure 1 was studied using 4D STEM diffraction (Figure 2). In Figures 2a and 2b, the nanotube and its raw total electron diffraction pattern are displayed. The yellow double-sided arrow indicates the orientation of the nanotube. The pattern consists of several almost ring-like diffractions with two distinct signals near the primary beam corresponding to the interlayer distances (002), characteristic for nanotubes in general. Figure 2c shows interlocked hexagonal and rectangular markings overlaid on the same electron diffraction pattern representing some diffractions of WS_2 and WTe_2 lattices, respectively. The pair of red hexagons are typical for the indication of the chiral WS_2 nanotube (displayed in Figure 4S).^[37] Multiple green rectangles represent the (120) diffractions of the WTe_2 nanotubular walls with various chiral angles. In Figure 2d, diffractions of selected spots on the nanotube (see 1.-3. black cross-marks in 2a corresponding to 2d 1.-3.) are displayed together with simulated patterns to fully understand the pattern's complexity.

The first spot (Figure 2d 1.) was acquired from the outer WTe_2 layers. The most prominent signals are from the (00 l) planes and specifically (002) signals. Their position approximately corresponds to the interlayer distance of 0.7-0.8 nm. Moreover, further lines 01 l and 02 l are visible. The limited visibility of some diffraction spots is due to the folding angle (chiral vector) of layers and the angle of the lattice towards the e-beam. The second selected spot (Figure 2d 2.) is from the middle of the nanotube, where the WS_2 lattice is visualized from the directions $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 001 \rangle$. There are also diffractions of WTe_2 lattice in the ED; however, for clarity, only the reflections WS_2 signals are marked by red hexagons and red numbering. The specific diffractions of WTe_2 (01 l and 02 l) are not present due to the curvature of the nanotube. On the other hand, lines (01 l) signals of WS_2 are clearly visible, specifically (011) diffractions of the $\langle 100 \rangle$ view. Importantly, the diffractions in the (00 l) line

have changed their position and intensity changes with respect to the WTe_2 counterpart in Figure 2d 1. The interlayer distance calculated from the position of (002) reflection corresponds to the WS_2 lattice 0.65-0.7. The interlayer distance difference between WS_2 and WTe_2 layers was confirmed directly in another nanotube (Figure 5S). Measuring a bundle of ten layers of WS_2 and WTe_2 provided 7.18 and 6.26 nm distances, respectively, corresponding to an average of 7.18 and 6.26 Å per layer. The whole selected pattern (Figure 2d 2.) is then completed with two interlocked hexagons formed by diffractions of curved layers from the approximate (001) direction. The third part of Figure 2d (3.) was selected from the center of the nanotube, where diffraction signals originate predominantly from the (001) direction views (perpendicular to the hypothetical flat tungsten dichalcogenide layer). The almost ring-like diffractions are visible as in the overall diffraction (Figure 2b). The pattern was fitted with twisted red hexagons of WS_2 lattice and two green rectangles holding a 55° angle. This corresponds to Figure 1b where outer WTe_2 layers are observed along the $\langle 100 \rangle$ axis, and two layers below are tilted, showing a pattern resembling $\langle 110 \rangle$ or $\langle 320 \rangle$ that correspond to 60 or 55°, respectively. Indeed, in both the selected and complete patterns, other folding angles and diffractions are possible to observe, as indicated in Figure 2c. These could be explained by the inner WTe_2 layers or possibly even by other layers grown on the outer shell that were not directly observed in TEM. The selected area diffraction of different nanotube specimen, together with its TEM imaging, is displayed in Figure 6S.

Figure 2. 4D STEM diffraction analysis of $\text{WTe}_2@WS_2@WTe_2$ nanotube. a) STEM-EDS elemental mapping of the nanotube with localized points corresponding to point diffraction in d). b) raw total diffraction pattern of the nanotube. The yellow arrow marks the nanotube orientation. c) Partially marked total pattern by interlocked rectangles representing (120) diffractions in the WTe_2 lattice from (001) direction. d) point diffractions from the WTe_2 side layers (1.), inner WS_2 part (2.), and middle of the nanotube (3.). Signed diffractions approximately correspond to the matching simulated patterns below.

The specific nanotube analyzed so far has its inner layers consisting of the WTe_2 phase. This structural phenomenon and, specifically, its synthetic pathway were studied in some detail. As recently revealed by *in-situ* electron microscopy, the mechanism of the nanotube growth is based on mixed gas-solid and gas-gas phase reactions.^[34] Thanks to the anisotropic volatilization of the oxide core, cavities of the nascent nanotube are formed from the nanowhisker's tips and progress in time until a full nanotube is formed. Vapors of the oxide react with the H_2S and H_2 and deposit new layers within the cavities. This insight could be exploited for divergent reaction pathways. The sulfidation reaction of the $\text{W}_{18}\text{O}_{49}$ nanowhiskers could be prematurely disrupted, producing WS_2 layers-decorated $\text{W}_{18}\text{O}_{49}$ nanowhiskers. Subsequently, the tungsten oxide core independently reacted with H_2Te and tellurium vapors (see Scheme 1e), producing core-shell $\text{WTe}_2@WS_2$ nanotubes in distinguishable amounts. The WTe_2 layers were confined within the WS_2 shell without collapsing into plates, as observed by HRTEM and HRSTEM-HAADF/EDS (Figure 3). Thanks to van der Waals epitaxy, the WTe_2 layers were deposited onto the preexisting WS_2 walls, accommodating their curvature to the folded (WS_2) nanotubular template, copying their curvature, and eventually forming WTe_2 nanotube walls. As highlighted in Figures 3a (side view) and 3b (cross-section), six to eight layers of WTe_2 were deposited within the cavity of a WS_2 nanotube. The chemical differences are observable by contrast (HRSTEM-HAADF) images and interlayer distances (HRTEM). Using Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) processing, the interlayer spacing of 6.4 and 7.2 Å (by), correspond with the *d*-spacings of WS_2 and WTe_2 , respectively. The inset of Figure 3b shows the EDS elemental mapping of sulfur (red) and tellurium (green), clearly distinguishing between the two phases. Interestingly, the layers closer to the nanotube center are more polygonal, whereas the outer layers are round. The cross-section image shows an apparently partially filled cavity in the center of the lamella and an amorphous outer ring. These two zones are rich in tellurium and tungsten oxides are formed during the focused ion beam cutting, lift-out, and transport on air. The minor discrepancy between side (Figure 3a) and cross-section (Figure 3b) views was caused by slight flattening and oxidation of the air-sensitive WTe_2 during the focused ion beam processing. Figure 3c shows TEM analysis of the oxide-chalcogenides interface of the nascent $\text{WTe}_2@WS_2$ nanotube. The left part of the structure is a $\text{W}_{18}\text{O}_{49}$ nanowhisker with approximately 10 WS_2 layers on the surface. New WTe_2 layers in the right part of the image are growing out of the nanowhisker edge and deposited onto the WS_2 layers. This growth mode corresponds with the new “receding oxide core” mechanism observed *in situ* recently.^[34] Elemental STEM-HAADF and EDS mapping of the nanotube is shown in Figure 3d&e.

In analogy to the $WS_{2(1-x)}Se_{2x}$ nanotubes reported recently,^[38] $WS_{2(1-x)}Te_{2x}$ nanotubes with $x \leq 0.2$ were obtained by reacting $\text{W}_{18}\text{O}_{49}$ with a mixture of H_2S and tellurium vapors in the atmosphere of a forming gas and presented in some detail in the SI (Figure 7S).

Figure 3. Imaging of core-shell WTe₂@WS₂ multilayer nanotube. a) The TEM image of the preselected nanotube with two dashed lines indicating the phase interface between the WTe₂ core and WS₂ shell layers. b) Cross-section HAADF view of the nanotube from a). The apparently partially filled cavity is an artifact from surface oxidation formed during transport. The inset b) shows elemental STEM-EDS mapping of Sulfur (red) and Tellurium (green). c) TEM image of different nascent nanotube showing growing WTe₂ inner layers within the WS₂ shell from the internalized W₁₈O₄₉ oxide core. d) and e) show the same WTe₂@WS₂ nanotube from c) on different spot as STEM-HAADF and STEM-EDS elemental mapping, respectively.

Figure 4. WS₂@MoTe₂ nanotube

Figure 5. WTe₂@WS₂@MoTe₂ nanotube

Conclusion

Tungsten ditelluride was successfully reached in the form of a nanotube by depositing its layers onto the WS₂ nanotube substrate. The variability of the synthesis depends on the possible formulation of both WS₂@WTe₂ structures as WTe₂@WS₂. A combination of approaches also materializes exotic heterogenous WTe₂@WS₂@WTe₂ nanotubes. The structure of the nanotubular material was studied in detail by 4D STEM diffraction analysis, revealing the 2H/1T' interface between WS₂ and WTe₂ phases, respectively. Both deposited WTe₂ and target WS₂ layers are chiral. The mechanism of WTe₂@WS₂ formation was briefly studied. Reasons for the challenging synthesis of pure WTe₂ nanotube by conventional approaches were also revealed. The preparation and characterization of tellurium-substituted WS₂ nanotubes conclude the family of tungsten sulfide-telluride tubular nanostructures. Thanks to the extraordinary research and application interest in tungsten ditelluride, the reached materials promise a broad range of further characterization and utilization studies.

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Experimental

General

Inorganic WS₂ nanotubes and WO_{3-x} nanowhiskers coated with several WS₂ layers were synthesized according to the previously reported protocol.^[37] The high-temperature reductive sulfidations of W₁₈O₄₉ nanowhiskers were held in a flow reactor at 845 °C under a stream of H₂S and H₂ in nitrogen. The nanowhiskers encased within several WS₂ layers were produced when the sulfidation reaction was interrupted after 10 min of reaction time by swiftly extracting the quartz flow reactor from the hot zone. The fine powders of WO₃ and elemental tellurium were obtained from Merck. The flow reactor was equipped with a single heating source, providing a heat profile with a thermostatic area in the middle of the heat curve.

Core-Shell WS₂@WTe₂ nanotubes

Powders of WS₂ nanotubes (0.1 g) and WO₃ (0.1 g) were ground in a mortar, dispersed in methanol (UV grade), and ultrasonicated. The suspensions were left dry on air, and homogenized powders were transferred to a quartz boat. Mixed WS₂ nanotubes with WO₃ reacted at 800 °C, with tellurium placed in a cold zone (750 °C) in a flow of forming gas (5 % H₂, 110 ml.min⁻¹) for 30 minutes. WS₂ fullerene-like nanoparticles were processed in the same manner.

Core-Shell WTe₂@WS₂ and WTe₂@WS₂@WTe₂ nanotubes

Reversed core-shell nanotubes were accomplished by telluridation of WO_{3-x} nanowhiskers with several WS₂ layers. Reaction conditions were identical to the previous case. Alternatively, tris-layered structures were synthesized by telluridation of a powder mixture of WO_{3-x}@WS₂ and WO₃, similar to the protocol for WS₂@WTe₂.

Tellurium-doped WS₂ nanotubes

W₁₈O₄₉ nanowhiskers were prepared according to the previously reported protocol.^[41] The following are described in detail in the manuscript from the range of tested reaction conditions. The sulfidation-telluridation reaction of such nanowhiskers was performed at 800 °C by introducing a tellurium source in the cold zone (580°C). Tellurium vapors were transported in the stream of H₂S (2 vol.%), H₂ (5 vol.%), and nitrogen gases (total flow 112 ml.min⁻¹). The reaction was stopped after 30 minutes by swiftly extracting the sample in the quartz tube from the hot zone.

Tellurization of W₁₈O₄₉ nanowhiskers

W₁₈O₄₉ nanowhiskers were partially tellurized at 800 °C for 10 minutes, similar to the already mentioned cases. After reaching reaction time, the sample was extracted swiftly from the hot zone, left to cool down, and characterized by HRTEM and STEM-HAADF/EDS.

Cross-sections of preselected nanotubes

For the cross-sectional TEM lamella preparation, a Thermo Fisher Helios 5 FX microscope was used. The TEM-preselected nanotube was localized on a holey carbon grid. Amorphous carbon was selected for the deposition of a protection layer. This allows better recognition of the nanotube cross-section during the subsequent thinning due to the contrast between the nanotube (heavy elements) and the protection layer (carbon). Additional tungsten markers were embedded into the deposition layer to target the selected part of the nanotube precisely. All deposition steps were performed using electrons to avoid any initial beam damage caused by the gallium ions. Due to the electron-transparent and perforated nature of the carbon grid, the deposition process occurred also on the bottom part of the grid. The lamella was lifted out using a micromanipulator and subsequently transferred to a copper FIB grid. The thinning and polishing procedure was performed with FIB accelerating voltages ranging from 30 kV to 2 kV and beam currents ranging from 2 nA to 26 pA.

Transmission Electron Microscopy

Samples for TEM were prepared either as cross-sections or drop-casted suspensions formed by ultrasonication in methanol (UV grade). The TEM analysis was performed using a Thermo Fisher Scientific Talos F200X equipped with a SuperX EDS detector. Both transmission and scanning transmission modes used a high accelerating voltage of 200 kV and a beam current of 1 nA. TEM, STEM High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) and images of energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) chemical mapping were post-processed in the Velox and ImageJ software. Some measurements were executed on a double aberration-corrected Themis-Z microscope (Thermo Fisher Scientific Electron Microscopy Solutions, Hillsboro, USA, (TFS)) at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Zero-loss filtered 4D-STEM datasets were obtained with a CEOS CEFID (CEOS GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany) energy filter, equipped with a DECTRIS ELA (DECTRIS AG, Baden, Switzerland) hybrid-pixel array detector.

Raman Spectroscopy

Micro-Raman spectra were collected on a Horiba LabRAM HR Evolution (Horiba, France) spectrometer equipped with four lasers (325, 532, 633, and 785 nm). The system has an 800 mm focal length spectrograph with several interchangeable gratings and is mounted with an open electrode, front-illuminated, cooled CCD detector. The sample is placed under a modular microscope (Olympus BX-FM) with a suitable objective. For this work, an $\times 150$ NA 0.9 (Olympus Japan) objective with a spatial resolution better than 1 μm was used. The scattered light from the sample was dispersed on 600 and 1800 g/mm gratings, and the pixel resolution is 1.3 cm^{-1} and 0.35 cm^{-1} , respectively. Spectra were collected between 100 and 1200 cm^{-1} , with exposure of 15–20 s and two averages. Laser power was adjusted to avoid detector saturation or sample damage.